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MARDIYA J. BALAHIM, LPT, ED.D

Associate Professor II

Sulu State College

mardiyabalahim69@gmail.com

“MY FIRST BORN, SHARFIEYA”

No words can tell the magic there,
when I first saw you soft and fair.
held in my arms, so small, so new,
my world lift up because of you.

just watching you was pure delight,
a sparkling dream, a shining light.
your little smile, so sweet and true,
awakens life in all I do.

no words can tell the love I feel,
a love so deep, so bright, so real.
my first born child, my answered prayer,
a precious soul beyond compare.

I prayed for you with all my heart,
and god’s design played it’s perfect part.
your beauty shines with all you do,
my heart found love it never knew.

No words can tell how cries so small
can sound like a music through it all.
a touch upon your gentle face
makes life itself fall in place.

your warm embrace, your tiny sway,
enough to color everyday.
and when you smile, the heavens rise,
a burst of joy before my eyes.

No words can tell what filled my soul
when “Ney” you called me, soft, yet whole.
a simple sound, but sweet and clear,

a memory I hold so dear.

even if I stumble, fall,
that happiness outshines it all.
it lives within my heart to stay,
a love no time can take away.

my first born child, my heart's one plea,
my joy, my life, my melody.
the one I cherish, the one I adore,
SHARFIEYA.

